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D1.1 – Linking HIT2GAP and adding value to the main energy modelling approaches; a general view and the cases of ESP-R, EPBD and EW-S

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Executive Summary

HIT2GAP is inspired from the smartphone Android/ IOS paradigm and aims at developing a kind of an operating system for building energy applications. This OS like environment (called HIT2GAP platform) would then provide some basic functions to allow diverse applications (called HIT2GAP modules) to plug in and make use of them. Similar to Apple's IOS or Google's Android, where third-parties provide various applications on the "Apple Store" and "Google Play", HIT2GAP will also give the opportunity to third-parties to deploy their applications in the HIT2GAP APP Store (Figure 1).

Figure 1: HIT2GAP process description

The purpose of the deliverable D1.1 is three fold.

- To provide a concise, **birds-eye view of the HIT2GAP platform functionality.**
- To **elaborate on specific value adding aspects of HIT2GAP** that are highlighted in the project and have received some strong attention in the HIT2GAP approach; such are the various energy modeling tools used, the issue of behaviour and its relevance to energy management, the issue of IPMVP, etc..
- To **highlight how HIT2GAP addresses the "gap"** and contributes to closing it. It is here reminded that the major strategic ambition of HIT2GAP is to develop an open platform that can contribute to the **reduction of the so called "gap", i.e., the deviation between the prediction and actual building performance.**

D1.1 is a document highlighting the link between HIT2GAP and the energy modelling approaches while serving as an introduction to the HIT2GAP specifications. These specifications are provided in other deliverables and explain all the technologies included in the HIT2GAP solution.

The HIT2GAP specification spans several closely interrelated documents, which are essential towards a traditional three tier specification (data, functionality, user interface) and cover the

different levels of the platform architecture which is proposed in the project (CORE level-API level-MODULES level). These specifications are described in D1.2, D1.3, D1.4, D1.5, D1.6, D1.7 and D1.8 as follows:

- D1.2 is the deliverable where the data model / schema used in the platform is addressed (DATA incorporated in the CORE level). The deliverable D1.8 is also part of the data organization and administration as it provides the data management plan of the project in a more general way.
- D1.3, D1.4, D1.5 and D1.6 are the documents in which the advanced data treatment modules are described in relation to prediction, disaggregation, fault detection and diagnosis, building/energy simulation and user behaviour modelling (MODULES level);
- D1.7 is the deliverable where the visualization functionalities of HIT2GAP are described (USER INTERFACE which is located both at CORE level and MODULES level).

Finally, D1.9 will describe the whole methodology of HIT2GAP, the modules' functionality (FUNCTIONALITY) and the way these modules are integrated within the platform (API level). D1.9 will also describe how HIT2GAP provides answer to users' requirements and how it contributes to the energy performance gap reduction as a whole.

1 Introduction

D1.1 is focusing on introducing to the modelling work carried out in WP1 as well as highlighting the GAP concept and how the various modules defined within the platform may contribute to drastically reducing it. D1.1 also serves as an introduction to the detailed HIT2GAP specifications which are provided in other deliverables (D1.2, D1.3, D1.4, D1.5, D1.6, D1.7 and D1.8) and explain all the technologies included in the HIT2GAP solution.

1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this document is to:

- Provide a **concise, birds-eye view of the HIT2GAP platform functionality**.
- **Elaborate on specific value adding aspects of HIT2GAP** that are highlighted in the project and have received particular attention in the HIT2GAP approach; such are the various energy modeling tools used, the issue of behaviour and its relevance to energy management, the issue of IPMVP, etc..
- **Highlight how HIT2GAP addresses the “gap”** and contributes to closing it.

1.2 Overview of WP1

In order to highlight the interdependence of the deliverables in WP1 and present how these explicitly serve the specification of HIT2GAP, we will summarise below the WP deliverables and will highlight how these

- contribute to the HIT2GAP specification
- elaborate on some very specific aspects and components of HIT2GAP

D 1.1	This introductory document
D 1.2	The specification of the data model of HIT2GAP (Data layer of the specification)
D 1.3	Forecasting in HIT2GAP: An in depth presentation
D 1.4	Disaggregation in HIT2GAP: An in depth presentation
D 1.5	Energy modelling in HIT2GAP: An in depth presentation
D 1.6	Behaviour in HIT2GAP: An in depth presentation
D 1.7	The specification of the visualisation model of HIT2GAP (Presentation layer of the specification)
D 1.8	Data Management plan-Open access issues in HIT2GAP
D 1.9	The methodology of HIT2GAP (Functionality layer of the specification)

As one can notice

- the three layers of the specification are elaborated in D1.2, D1.7 and D1.9;
- key empowering concepts in HIT2GAP are in detail discussed in the rest of the deliverables and in particular D1.3, D1.4, D1.5 and D1.6;

D1.1 will focus on introducing to the modelling work carried out in WP1 as well as highlighting the GAP concept and how the various modules may contribute to drastically reducing it.

1.3 Organization of work

Understanding how HIT2GAP can address the “gap” will be discussed on a module per module basis; such modules were elaborated in Task1.1 and are to be in detail specified in WP1 and will be developed in the course of the project. It is with regard to these modules that the gap can be considered. Work in D1.1 was therefore carried out in parallel with D1.9 (module specification), which is also part of Task1.1.

T1.1 started from a collection of **available** modules as well as ideas for **new** modules that are in line with the broader goals of the project. This collection was done over standardized Adobe templates that were distributed by the task / deliverable manager to all the partners.

The layout of the modules is part of the functional specification of HIT2GAP laid out in D1.9.

After the module definition, partners where asked to systematically address and report on the module relevance with the “gap” reduction.

1.4 Contributions of partners

APINTECH has structured this report and has coordinated the collection of information from the application module providers (NBK, FISE, UDG, UOS, ENE, EGE) involved in this part of the HIT2GAP project, in order to highlight the:

- Added value of HIT2GAP
- Gap relevance

Specifically, partners' engagement in the configuration process of this report is summarized in tabular form:

Partner's Short name	Partner's Contribution to Deliverable
API	<p>Section 1</p> <p>Section 3: <i>3.1 General view</i> <i>3.5 The case of BIM</i> <i>3.6 The case of real time data management</i></p> <p>Section 4</p> <p>Section 5</p> <p>Section 6</p>

ENE	Section 3: 3.7 <i>The case of energy management (ISO 150001)</i> Section 5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multiple set-point control module's short description - Energy Management module's short description
FISE	Section 5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building performance simulation module's short description - Uncertainty Analysis and Sensitivity Analysis module's short description - Fault detection and diagnosis (FDD) module's short description
UoS	Section 3: 3.2 <i>The case of ESP-R</i> Section 5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building performance assessment module's short description
NBK	Section 2 Section 5
BRE	Section 3: 3.3 <i>The case of EPBD</i>
CYR	Section 3: 3.4 <i>The case of EW-S</i> Section 5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simulator –Calibration module's short description - Forecasting module's short description - RET simulation module's short description
ZUT	Section 5: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HIT2GAP BIM module's short description

1.5 Report structure

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- Initially, an executive summary of the work is provided.
- **Section 1** is the current introduction.
- **Section 2** introduces a birds-eye view of the HIT2GAP platform.
- **Section 3** discusses **the added value HIT2GAP brings to specific key issues** that are greatly emphasized in the project such as well-known simulators (ESP-R, Energy+, IDA-ICE, Modelica, FMI) used for energy modeling, the EBPD, BIM, IPMVP, real-time aspects as well as energy management and certification according to ISO 50001.
- **Section 4** provides a brief discussion of the key topic of behaviour and how this is positioned in HIT2GAP.
- **Section 5** summarizes how HIT2GAP contributes to closing the gap.
- **Section 6** is the conclusion of the work.

2 HIT2GAP Platform and Modules

The main idea of HIT2GAP is to design and implement a generic open platform (Figure 1) where third parties provide analytic software and services, including simulation services, to optimize building energy performance and reduce the gap between the conceptual design intent and actual operating performance.

In fact, and similar to Apple’s IOS or Google’s Android, where third-parties provide various applications on the “Apple Store” and “Google Play”, HIT2GAP will also give the opportunity to third-parties to deploy their applications in the HIT2GAP APP Store [1] (i.e., simulator calibration, user behavior, forecasting, etc.).

In order to achieve the scope of the HIT2GAP project, the platform architecture is formed by 5 distinct levels:

1. **Field level**, which mainly consists of all data sources existing in a building, i.e., installed BMS, weather forecasting, usage/occupant data, etc.
2. **Management level**, which includes the HIT2GAP third-party applications i.e., Simulation-calibration, HVAC calibration, Disaggregation, User behaviour, Energy management, Forecasting, Building performance assessment, Fault Detection and Diagnosis (FDD), and Multiple set-point control, etc.
3. **Core platform level** that contains a set of core functionalities enabling connectivity to BMS and alternative devices/sources, data collection, preprocessing and normalization, and open access to third-party applications.
4. **Back-end level**, responsible to extend the functionality of the core platform and management levels services.
5. **End-user level**, responsible of the interaction between the end-user and the HIT2GAP services.

Figure 2: HIT2GAP process description

2.1 The HIT2GAP architecture description

Before defining the HIT2GAP functional architecture, several studies were made on two different domains' architectures that are strongly related to the HIT2GAP solution:

- Architectures related to Smart Buildings domain
- Architectures related to Business Analytics domain

On one hand, smart buildings domain was chosen since the HIT2GAP solution can act as a generic smart BMS tool that can connect to different equipment and data sources, and manage the collected data through a centralized interface. On the other hand, business analytics solution architectures were analyzed because the HIT2GAP project aims to integrate advanced big data processing, and thus support big data advanced analysis and operations.

In the smart building domain several architectures were explored:

- Microsoft smart building architecture [2]
- Niagara framework [3]
- CASCADE architecture [4]
- User- Centric Building Automation Platform [5]

The analysis showed that none of the mentioned architectures can integrate different type of applications/modules developed by different parties and facilitate the information exchange between them. Only one, the one described in [5], is designed by modules that can be connected together, and replaced or added without affecting the rest of the system. Moreover, few are the solutions (the ones described in [4] and [5]) that are able to ensure seamless communication between the lower and the upper layers of their architectures, and are easily extendable to meet other business requirements.

From the business analytics domain, two architectures have been focused on:

- A Five Layered BI Architecture [6]
- Real Time Big Data Analytics (RTBDA) Architecture [7]

Although these architectures include advanced processing, none of them:

- Ensures the integration among diverse systems/devices,
- Is applicable and adaptable in different environments and in particularly to smart buildings domain,
- Ensures seamless communication between their components,
- Is designed by modules that can be connected together and modified without affecting the others.

Based on the analysis made on those different architectures, and in order to meet the HIT2GAP solution requirements, the HIT2GAP platform is defined by a modular architecture with 5 levels:

Figure 3: HIT2GAP architecture

2.1.1 Field Level

The **field level** contains all the physical equipment/sensors installed in a building, and data sources connected to the building (i.e., user behavior, weather forecasts, building data, etc.). On this level, data can be:

- Part of the installed BMS (i.e. HVAC system, energy meters, water meters, etc.).
- Part of traditional repositories not included in a BMS and stored in different format, i.e. XML, Excel Sheets, MySQL, etc.
- Sensor readings which represent the values of the sensors (traditional or advanced devices) that are not connected to the BMS, i.e. multimedia cameras, smartphones, smart tablets, humidity sensors, etc.
- Environmental information which are external data, i.e., weather forecasts, solar radiations data, energy cost data, etc.
- Building information such as: Orientation data, construction data (i.e., building levels, walls, doors, windows, etc.), etc. These information will be represented through the IFC format, a standard known in the building industry.
- Building occupancy information that will include usage/occupant data i.e., building operational scheduled activities, occupant profile (age, gender, work schedule, etc.), etc.

Data related to the installed BMS, traditional repositories, sensor readings, and environmental information will be connected to the HIT2GAP platform through the PLAT.ONE connector which has the capability to align with their different format and structure.

The other type of data sources will be integrated into the platform through a set of drivers that will be defined later.

2.1.2 Management Level

The **management level** acts as the HIT2GAP applications store, contains third-party applications (the HIT2GAP modules developed by the partners in a first stage). These applications/modules are physically implemented outside the HIT2GAP core platform. These modules use the core platform as a middleware between them and the data sources of the field level. In fact, and similar to Apple's IOS or Google's Android, where third-parties provide various applications on the "Apple Store" and "Google Play", HIT2GAP will also give the opportunity to third-parties to deploy their applications in the HIT2AP APP Store (i.e., simulator calibration, user behavior, forecasting, etc.), using APIs defined in the core platform, while disregarding the specifications of the physical devices and other services. In other words, any provided application can be deployed in any type of buildings regardless of the installed BMS' infrastructure.

Moreover, the HIT2GAP applications store contains also an "app downloader" service that allows user to install applications on end-user machines (e.g. computers, mobiles, tablets, etc.).

2.1.3 Core Platform Level (Middleware)

Nowadays, most critical issues arise when defining a middleware layer between the field level and the management level, which bears most of the responsibility for supporting application requirements and, at the same time, managing a wide and possibly heterogeneous set of devices. As a matter of fact, interoperability issues arise on different levels:

- On the **field level**, how to render different proprietary devices/sensors compatible and allow them to communicate between each other when they are developed by different manufacturers and communicate through different protocols. For example, a temperature sensor that supports Modbus protocol can only send the data measured only to the controller that can exchange messages via the same protocol. The temperature received by the controller cannot be sent to different type of devices or systems unless the controller is able to handle their communication protocols. Moreover, other barriers may exist due to the configurations and technical specifications designed by different manufacturers. The same issues arise whenever a new source of data needs to be deployed in the building.
- On the **management level**, how to allow third-party applications to communicate since they are being developed on different environments/platforms (i.e., NetBeans and Eclipse for JAVA coding, Komodo and PyDev for Python, etc.), and written in different languages (i.e., JAVA, C#, Python, etc.) without using common libraries and services that unify their development and deployment. Therefore, any integration of

new applications requires development from scratch and coding skills to adapt the application to the necessary platform, and thus exhausting a long period of time, human resources, and higher financial cost.

- **Between the field level and the management level**, how to allow applications from third-parties to communicate with third-party devices since the infrastructure level choices are heavily dependent on the application requirements, and vice versa. On one hand, any modification applied on the field level (i.e., additional type of devices) requires an adaptation of the applications and services on the management level. On the other hand, any changes embedded in the applications of the management level, affect the configurations of the physical equipment on the field level.

To overcome the above issues, HIT2GAP follows a horizontal layering, double blind and model-driven approach [8]:

- On one hand, a horizontal layering on the field level is defined through a drivers' layer in the core platform that allows new devices to be added and connected regardless of the upper levels. On the other hand, a horizontal layering on the management level is defined through the design and implementation of web APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) that can be used by different applications to communicate with the lower levels and retrieve collected data.
It is important to note that the use of web APIs renders HIT2GAP independent of any environment/platform and programming language.
- Double blind, by making the applications and services in the management level independent from the technologies deployed in the field level. In fact, separating the physical level (field level) from the application level (management level) will be ensured in the core platform through the use of different drivers (field level side), web APIs (management level side) and an abstraction layer between them that defines a unified data model, allowing data from different sources to be stored and retrieved by management services/modules.
- Model driven, by integrating an abstraction layer between the drivers and the APIs that provides a semantic rich representation of the building infrastructure (data sources), which is the key enabling factor for the double blind approach. This semantic representation (defined as an Ontology in our case) stands as an abstraction component between the physical technical specifications and their functional information.

From these perspectives, the core platform level constitutes the main contribution of the HIT2GAP architecture. It acts as a middleware that ensures the interoperability between all the different levels, primary due to the integration of a drivers' layer, an Ontology that effectively separates the applications requirements from the technical specifications of the installed devices and an APIs' layer. With these separations, interoperability is ensured, since applications may be added, updated or migrated anytime, and the field components can also be modified with little or no impact on the higher levels.

The HIT2GAP core defines several layers:

- **Data Collection**

It is responsible for the data collection and includes a drivers/data connectors' layer and a data model layer.

- The **drivers/data Connectors' layer** contains different drivers and connectors that connect to the data sources existing in the field level (e.g., PLAT.ONE is used as a connector to the pilot sites of the HIT2GAP). These connectors include all specific information related to the technologies used in the field level (i.e., communications protocols, type of devices, configurations, etc.). This covers the horizontal approach paradigm, allowing devices to be added and removed (horizontally) as required without affecting other levels.
- The **HIT2GAP model layer** plays an essential role in effectively separating the lower field level from the upper core platform level, and provides a semantic interoperability between all the architecture components.

This layer includes a data model and a storage space:

- The HIT2GAP data model is based on a semantic representation (in our case Ontologies). It contains, on one hand, technical and functional information on all types of equipment and devices available in the field level (i.e., what each device does, what type of data these devices capture, how these devices and equipment are connected, etc.) which is used to store the collected data, and on the other hand, information regarding the I/O of the HIT2GAP modules that will be used to retrieve and store data to/from the upper level applications and services (e.g., the predicted data from the forecasting module can be stored and then retrieved by a visualization module afterwards, such as the Innoxia module).

The main advantage of using Ontologies is to unify and normalize the data between all the architecture components. For example, on the field level, if the birth date of building occupants is retrieved from a data source "A" in the following format: dd/mm/yyyy, and from another data source "B" as follows: mm/dd/yyyy, the Ontology can define a unified format for the birth date and thus removes data ambiguity between the different sources.

The data model will be as generic and complete as possible to cover the field and management levels requirements.

- The storage space is used to store all the data collected from the field level and the management level based on the HIT2GAP data model. The storage space can be on the cloud or on a dedicated server based on the specifications and requirements of the HIT2GAP approach and business model.

- **Basic Services Layer**

This layer includes the basic services of the HIT2GAP platform, which are described as follow:

- The collection and data storage service allows the storage of collected data from the field level. The storage can be done according to a well-defined data

structure (unified format) and should meet the requirements of HIT2GAP data model (the Ontology). Moreover, it is responsible of updating the HIT2GAP data storage whenever new data is available.

- The data preprocessing service is used to clean and prepare the data before being analyzed in more advanced phases, and includes 3 sub-services:
 - A service that handles outliers and missing data. Missing data can be corrected using extrapolation, interpolation or aggregation functions.
 - A quality service responsible for checking the reliability of the data collected or being processed (e.g. if the captured temperature value is 13°C and after 10 minutes it became 32°C, this shows a low data quality, and thus influences the quality of the analysis).
 - A data frequency standardization service that allows:
 - Rounding the data acquisition time (e.g. if the value of the indoor humidity value is collected every 15 minutes as follows: 12:11, 12:26, 12:41, etc., and the temperature is captured following other time slots: 12:12, 12:28, 12:42, etc., the service permits rounding the time of acquisition of those data values: 12:00, 12:15, 12:30, etc.)
 - Users to predefine the desired frequencies (per hour, per day, per month, etc.)
 - The normalization of data time acquisition either to the lowest frequency (e.g. per second) or a higher frequency (e.g. per hour).
- The alert service is used to signal alerts (if occurred) at each data stage: On the acquisition, storage and pre-processing, according to predefined rules. Some examples of alerts:
 - Alerts indicating that the data value was not acquired; this problem can be caused by a malfunction of an equipment or a system.
 - Alerts indicating that the value has not been stored in the database; this can be caused by a data format problem.
 - Alerts on data reliability, and thus the quality of the analysis will be affected.
- The data anonymization service is responsible of protecting the sensitive and private data used in the HIT2GAP project. For example, it can include encryption functionalities on the personal data related to building occupants.

- **Information Layer**

This layer is mainly responsible for reasoning on the Ontology (the data model) using building indicators to elaborate meaningful information related to building energy management. At this stage, this layer remains undefined as the priority falls on the main data model that is required before we can define the reasoning process.

- **API Layer**

It is responsible for defining an interface that will be used by the consortium and other third-parties to adapt their tools to HIT2GAP. It contains APIs accessible by the management level applications and services. The functionalities offered by those

common APIs ensure the interoperability of different applications and services on the upper level since any additional or required application can use the APIs to connect to the HIT2GAP data storage, send and retrieve any required information without affecting other applications or services. The HIT2GAP APIs, JSON API and/or XML API, will be used mainly to integrate any module defined by third-parties. It is conceived as a web service independent from any platform and development language. This will allow third-parties to integrate their modules using their specific development expertise. To simplify the integration of modules, a specification document will be provided detailing the different queries and functionalities of the APIs. The output data will be formatted in JSON and/or XML, based on the specifications of the API and the data collected within the platform. Whether a visualization or a treatment module is being developed for HIT2GAP, it will use the HIT2GAP APIs to send a request to retrieve or store data collected by the core platform from the pilot sites. The APIs will send a response with the corresponding data.

It is critical to note that the modules will communicate vertically with each other through the core platform. They will not communicate directly with each other, otherwise they are considered a single module.

2.1.4 Back-End Level

The field, core platform and management levels, are considered as the backbone of the HIT2GAP architecture. In order to extend their functionalities, a back-end level is added to extend both core platform and management levels services.

This level contains the following 2 layers:

- **Core Back-End Layer**

It is responsible for extending the services of the core platform and it includes:

- Basic services extender to extend the basic services of the platform.
- API extender to extend the functionalities of the existing APIs (JSON API and/or XML API) or to add new types of APIs that may be needed in the future.
- Model extender to extend the HIT2GAP data model with new concepts and properties to accommodate the specifications of the management and field levels.
- Drivers/Connectors extender to add new types of connectors that may be required in the future to connect to new types of data sources, or extend the capabilities of the existing connectors.

- **Management Back-End Layer**

This layer extends the management level services. It includes the app extender that allows adding new third-party applications/modules to the HIT2GAP platform and update existing ones with new features.

2.1.5 End-User Level

The interaction between the end-user and the HIT2GAP backbone services will be done through the end-user level that contains services related to both the core platform and management levels, and includes the following 2 layers:

- **HIT2GAP Control Panel Layer**

It is responsible for controlling and visualizing several services offered by the HIT2GAP core platform, and includes:

- A data model visualization service used to visualize the HIT2GAP Ontology (i.e., the concepts, how they are related, etc.).
- An alert management service to manage the alerts occurred during data manipulation and processing.
- Basic configurations that allow the modifications of the services' basic parameters (i.e., setting the frequency data time acquisition).

- **Management Visualization Layer**

It contains visualization applications/modules offered by the HIT2GAP third-parties. These modules allow the interaction and communication between the third-party applications of the management level and the end-user.

To sum up, HIT2GAP is a generic, modular, and scalable solution for building energy management that follows 3 design methodologies: Horizontal layering, double blind and model-driven approach:

- Horizontal layering, through (i) the use of a Drivers' layer that support any type of device, and (ii) API services responsible to ensure the interoperability between applications and services of the upper level
- Double blind, by integrating an abstraction level that ensures interoperability between the field level technical specifications and the management level applications' requirements
- Model driven, since it includes a semantic rich representation (an Ontology) that stands as a unified data model abstracting the components from the physical level.

It is important to note that due to time limitations, the first version of the HIT2GAP project will be a light version offering the basic functionalities required to run the modules of the partners and to connect to the pilot sites.

Several services such as the ones included in the back-end level will be developed later.

3 The added value of HIT2GAP

3.1 General view

The main purpose of HIT2GAP is to elaborate and develop new methodologies and tools for the better assessment of energy use within a building or a block of buildings in order to minimize the gap between the theoretical and measured values. In its essence, HIT2GAP aims at an open approach for A NEW GENERATION OF BMS SOLUTIONS with plug and play analytics tools and modular services using a win-win strategy (between service providers, BMS manufacturers and cutting-edge SMEs).

In other words, SMEs can develop and integrate their tools, algorithms or services within a holistic open framework and HIT2GAP uses its platform and the integrated tools to provide a new generation of BMS.

HIT2GAP framework gets its inspiration from the smartphone Android and IOS platforms that provide a solution allowing applications to be developed separately from the platform itself and then easily integrated (Figure 3).

In this section we will discuss certain value adding aspects of HIT2GAP with regard to energy modeling as well as other scientific and practice areas in building energy management.

Figure 4: Overview concept of HIT2GAP platform

3.2 The case of ESP-R

Building performance simulation (BPS) is currently used in the design of large commercial buildings, but it is rarely applied in the building operation phase where it could play a central role in improving building performance. HIT2GAP supports the effective use of BPS in the building operation phase, by integrating building performance assessment modules in to the platform.

The modularity of HIT2GAP provides the bases for rapid prototyping of innovative services based on dynamic BPS aiming at the improvement of building energy performance. The modularity of the HIT2GAP platform will be demonstrated by the implementation of three modules using BPS, developed using the whole building simulation program ESP-r and also using models based on the Modelica language. Services provided by these modules will allow:

1. the identification of most probable reasons for the performance gap,
2. the calibration of BPS models using monitored data provided by the platform,
3. the evaluation of performance using standard performance assessment methods
4. the evaluation of design and operation alternatives to improve the performance of the building during the operation phase.

These services will provide a valuable contribution to improve the performance of existing buildings, but they will particularly demonstrate the capabilities of the HIT2GAP platform towards the integration of BPS in the building operation phase.

The availability of building monitoring data in the HIT2GAP platform makes it the ideal environment to deploy services based on BPS, where service developers can retrieve data about current building performance and use such data in their simulations (as boundary conditions, constraints, targets). The visualization modules of HIT2GAP offer new possibilities to communicate simulation results to a variety of stakeholders involved in the building operation.

In the future, the HIT2GAP platform will further support the development of variety of services based on BPS, such as benchmarking for commissioning, fault detection and diagnosis during commissioning and operation, predictive control for HVAC and for the operation of responsive building elements (shading devices and materials capable of changing properties over time). The synergy between HIT2GAP and dynamic BPS is mutually beneficial and aggregates value to all those willing to improve the energy performance of building in the operation phase.

3.3 The case of EPBD

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) was brought into force on 4 January 2003 with the aim of promoting improvement in the energy performance of buildings (within the EU) through cost-effective measures [9].

EPBD

HIT2GAP supports the EPBD by providing a means of enhancing the energy performance of buildings - by influencing factors which are not normally subject to optimisation - through the provision of appropriate information (potentially detailed information) about the 'real time' running performance of a building.

There are four main aspects to the EPBD:

1. **Establishment of a calculation methodology:** Member States must implement a methodology for calculating the energy performance of buildings, taking account of all factors that influence energy use; if the HIT2GAP approach is shown to benefit buildings in practice, the presence of such a system could be taken into account in such algorithms.
2. **Minimum energy performance requirements:** there must be regulations that set minimum energy performance requirements for new buildings and for large existing buildings when they are refurbished; HIT2GAP has the potential to demonstrate performance and to show where improvements can best be made during operation. Each country can implement either requirements for energy "modelling" of performance or to measure energy use in practice. Both approaches provide a ranking and allow for comparison. HIT2GAP would allow an extension to this EPBD approach by leading to real improvements. Initially this would need to be voluntary, however future updates of the EPBD or national approaches may invoke the type of approach enabled by HIT2GAP.
3. **Energy performance certificate:** there must be an energy performance certificate made available whenever buildings are constructed, sold or rented out; such certification could include approved HIT2GAP systems. This is similar to point 2 above, where HIT2GAP leads to improvements to building performance through better management and technical changes to the operation.
4. **Inspections of boilers and air-conditioning:** there must be regulations to require inspections of boilers and heating systems (or an alternative system of providing advice as discussed below), and inspection of air conditioning systems; HIT2GAP, if used to monitor HVAC, could potentially monitor the running efficiency of systems, and in doing so help to determine whether equipment is performing satisfactorily.

SBEM

SBEM (The Simplified Building Energy Model) is used in some countries as a means of certifying buildings for energy performance. For example in the UK, SBEM is the national calculation methodology for non-domestic buildings. It may be used for new buildings and for assessment or refurbishments of existing buildings. It predicts the consumption of building services, including HVAC, and rates buildings in relation to standard benchmarks, and it is an approved tool for supporting the EPBD requirement for a calculation methodology. It makes use of relatively simple algorithms, but it is continually evolving to take new technologies into account. Typical examples of new technologies might include new types of efficient lighting or renewable energy systems but it also has the potential to take into consideration better ways of controlling building services.

SBEM is a compliance tool for building regulation purposes. The energy 'model' and software associated with SBEM (iSBEM) is non-dynamic, allowing only a static view of energy use over a standardised year for its climatic exposure. However, the output from SBEM, either as an Energy Performance Certificate or output file provides a view of the building performance (energy use normalised to a building area and carbon dioxide emissions). It can be used to compare against the monitored performance and can help building managers to set a target or benchmark to improve the performance of their building.

BREEAM

SBEM also supports environmental performance rating systems such as BREEAM, as BREEAM takes energy efficiency into account in its overall assessment of buildings and premises. BREEAM, in addition, assesses the environmental impacts of building materials. In the overall BREEAM assessment of a building or estate, control systems such as HIT2GAP could be taken into account when evaluating the overall score for the building, provided the particular control system is recognised by BREEAM or suitably certified.

BREEAM In-Use International is an assessment method which assists property investors, owners, managers and occupiers to drive sustainable improvements through operational efficiency, including how to continually manage the operation of their building effectively. It is suitable for all existing commercial type buildings. Currently, the In-Use standard does not apply to residential dwellings.

It benefits investors, owners, landlords, facilities managers and occupiers by:

- reducing operational costs and increasing efficiency
- enhancing asset value and increasing market demand
- helping to attract tenants and occupiers
- improving the wellbeing, productivity and satisfaction of people working in the building
- helping bridge the 'performance gap' between modelled outputs and operational outputs
- providing independent third party certification of a building's sustainability
- contributing to corporate social responsibility, business reporting and sustainable business leadership.

BREEAM In-Use International is an online rating tool that allows users to register buildings, assess and certify the building performance. A dynamic scoring platform and reporting section allows the user to track and improve the performance of their building or portfolio of buildings. The BREEAM In-Use International standard is applied internationally. A common set of questions allows the user to compare assets with each other no matter where they are located. In countries where we are affiliated with an International Partner, a locally adapted version of BREEAM In-Use is available. Please view our Technical Standards Tool to find out which In-Use standard is applicable within your country.

BREEAM In-use is the component of the BREEAM Family that has most relevance to HIT2GAP, essentially both are seeking to do the same thing, i.e. to make improvements to buildings. BREEAM In-use has a wider remit than HIT2GAP, which is more focussed on energy and allows for the creation of a platform.

HIT2GAP can complement BREEAM In-use and could potentially allow the outputs from the different models and monitoring modules to be used as evidence in a BREEAM In-use assessment. Certification of HIT2GAP could potentially be realised through the BREEAM platform, although this would need a more detailed investigation and assessment prior to implementation.

3.4 The case of EW-S

The Energy Warden Simulator (EW-S) is a simulation environment which serves as a design aid or decision support tool for the design or retrofit of new or existing energy infrastructures in buildings through the estimation and prediction of energy production (both thermal and electrical), grid exchanges, energy storage and, finally, energy end-use (both for renewable and conventional energy systems).

EW-S includes energy production and energy storage models which take account of the behaviour of the end users (thermal and energy consumption profiles), modelling of energy consuming devices (heating, cooling), energy production systems (solar-PV, solar water heating, solar space heating, geothermal etc.) and energy storage (hot water tanks, batteries, etc.).

All EW-S models have hourly time step and are designed to estimate accurately the energy produced, stored and consumed from RETs based on historical and location data. To achieve a high accuracy, data are used from performance results derived in the certification Test Reports for the specific RET systems.

To execute RET simulations the following critical design parameters are required: historical meteorological data, building space availability data, energy use profiles and pricing data, specific RET configuration technical data, RET equipment installation data and, finally, the applicable financing conditions.

The simulator provides optimal sizing of RETs systems and its components in new installations and retrofits based on user preferences. The EW-S users are Building Managers, Energy Consultants, RET System Designers and manufacturers.

3.5 The case of BIM

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is one of the most promising developments in the architecture, engineering and construction (AEC) industries [10]. BIM represents the process of development and use of a computer generated model to simulate the planning, design, construction and operation of a building facility. The resulting model is a data-rich, object-oriented, intelligent and parametric digital representation of the facility, from which views and data appropriate to various users' needs can be extracted and analyzed to generate information that can be used to make decisions and to improve the process of delivering the facility [11].

The proposed definition of the International Commission BIM Standards (National BIM Standards Committee - NBIMS) refers:

"Building Information Modeling (BIM) is a digital representation of physical and functional characteristics of a facility. A BIM is a shared knowledge resource for information about a facility forming a reliable basis for decisions during its life-cycle; defined as existing from earliest conception to demolition." [12]

In this Framework of the HIT2GAP project, the obtained Building Information Model combines the element or space temperature/humidity/energy usage available (current and historical data) but also the variance from design along with the manufacturers details, as built drawings, planned and

reactive maintenance details, spare parts and maintenance procedures, in order to predict accurately building energy loads and consumption along its lifecycle and to support decision making during different stages in the life of the buildings.

Within the plug & play approach for integrating tools and applications, the novel HIT2GAP system will offer a BIM tool by Zutec for the Integration of gathered, live and historical data into a 3D model for the energy performance assessment.

The BIM tool will be enriched by "real performance" experience to make a holistic and comprehensive approach for accurate simulation.

3.6 The case of real time data management

HIT2GAP is essentially a real time platform; it could hardly be possible otherwise. Real time data are that describe various aspects of the actual building performance. They are therefore vital in understanding actual building performance and making any gap assessment.

Almost all HIT2GAP modules include a real time element or benefit from real time data treatment provided by other modules. As example, total energy consumption in time, collected via a suitable energy meter of the aggregated energy information, is depicted in Figure 4. IPMVP considerations can be easily plugged into such a real time platform, allowing a much better, accurate interpretation of data that would offset external parameters such as weather, occupancy, etc. that, if unaccounted for, may distort our assessments.

In addition HIT2GAP will treat the diversity of the origins of real time data; these may reside in existing systems, but may need to be independently captured. They may result from traditional sensors but also from more advanced pathways (smartphones, etc.)

A major success metric will be the extent to which HIT2GAP may interface with diverse data sources which will no doubt increase exponentially as the IoT revolution takes off and enters its true growth phase.

Figure 5: Total energy consumption in time, collected via a suitable energy meter

3.7 The case of energy management (ISO 50001)

In this context of the HIT2GAP project, the effective Energy Management System (EnMS) of a building - embracing the whole system incorporating both the envelope components and any energy infrastructure - is becoming central in the process and needful as well.

In HIT2GAP, **EnMS** is considered since the design and commissioning phases, and - whether a Building Automation System (BAS) governs a building or only a monitoring system is installed, or nothing, the **EnMS** is intend as a "live process" which is supported by a standard methodology and effective tools to:

- Manage dynamically the Energy Action Plan (**EAP**), related to the current operational phase,
- Evaluate how the choices made during the design and commissioning phases are demonstrating to be (currently) effective.
- Evaluate continuous upgrade of building energy infrastructures that make feasible the implementation of up-to-date technology with financial availability in a way that energy and costs savings pay make profitable the investments to do.

However, tools managing only energy data monitoring or building control functions does not respond nowadays to the thirst of customers that are looking for more scalable and standardized features, also when a detailed energy consumption report with simple technical advices is generated.

Thus, although not explicitly related with energy/costs savings, the effective **EnMS** has to take care of:

- Providing an operative organizational level that makes possible to assign actions to staff's people and to track, control and review any ongoing action selected for implementation (*action management*)
- Share information within the Organization (*document management*).

Within the plug & play approach for integrating tools and applications, the novel HIT2GAP system will offer a devoted tool for Energy Management (Figure 5) that will be independent from the building's type or size, as well as from any specific technology.

This tool will be designed to match the core principles of the ISO 50001 standard and it will supports the implementation to make a holistic and comprehensive EnMS, while becoming efficient, effective and transparent.

In particular, the **Energy planning** process, which is a key step in establishing an EnMS, supports the **Energy Review** process though its unique **Energy Flow Assessor (EFA)** allowing Energy Sources and Energy Uses to be analysed for easily identify any related *Improvement Opportunities*: from there, Action Plans and Objectives & Targets can be defined and tracked.

Figure 6: The Energy Management module through the integration between Enerit software and HIT2GAP system

4 HIT2GAP and behaviour

User behaviour in buildings has been shown to have large impacts on space heating, cooling and ventilation demand, energy consumption of lighting and space appliances, and building controls. Careless behaviour can add one-third to a building's designed energy performance while conscious behaviour can save a third [13]. Of course, changing user behaviour should not lead to discomfort (relative restriction of human activities, downgrading of working conditions, decay of the quality of services offered).

In an extensive report published by the European Environment Agency [14], the key impact findings are detailed and the following table – “Potential energy savings due to measures targeting behaviour” is presented:

Table 1: Potential energy savings due to measures targeting behaviour

Intervention	Range of energy savings	
Feedback	5 – 15 %	Although certain rebound effects ¹ are identified the key result is a radically different view on user behaviour which might lead to changes and economies between 20 - 40%. Changes are not deemed realistic any more in the realm of physics and building construction. Our materials and systems are now well optimized.
Direct feedback (including smart meters)	5 – 15 %	
Indirect feedback (e.g. enhanced billing)	2 – 10 %	
Feedback and target setting	5 – 15 %	
Energy audits	5 – 20 %	
Community-based initiatives	5 – 20 %	
Combination interventions (of more than one)	5 – 20 %	

If one takes a closer look to the kind interventions suggested by the above important report they the word "feedback and notification would be the highest action priority.

In HIT2GAP behaviour receives a prominent position. To this extent, a special module has been designed, which provides several types of modular functionality. These are independent; the module is modular itself and one can deploy whatever extension one may wish to introduce.

Although module in terms of functionality, there are some common aspects running through all sub modules.

- **Notification upon wastage event detection;** just as the literature suggests HIT2GAP places a key emphasis on user notification. Whenever a wastage event is detected the respective notification is issued to the respective user. A number of events will be modelled, without this being restrictive on adding further events in the future (see the video below for more info on the events currently supported).

¹ an intervention having a simultaneous negative impact on another intervention

- **Technology modifications;** this is an extension to simple user feedback and notification. Here, we do not only *notify* the user but we also **technically implement some solution to manage the wastage event**.

In addition to this event driven functionality the behaviour module addresses also the innovative concept of user mood.

- **The modelling and the assessment of mood;** this is an innovative dimension that will allow a better understanding of user mood with all the important repercussions that go with this development with regard to a better understanding of behaviour.

In short, HIT2GAP places prime and state of the art focus on behaviour. Besides the broad discussion above, **a special video has been developed to highlight the HIT2GAP approach with regard behaviour**. Figures 6-8 show some screenshots of the video description of HIT2GAP Behaviour module.

This video can be accessed here:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1vxL19hUPLU&feature=em-upload_owner

Figure 7: Full video description of HIT2GAP Behaviour module

Figure 8: Screenshot of the created video description of HIT2GAP Behaviour module (Statement of Purpose)

Figure 9: Screenshot of the created video description of HIT2GAP Behaviour module (Events to be triggered)

5 HIT2GAP and the 'Gap' reduction

The performance gap is a relatively new concept that can be defined as the difference between the energy consumption anticipated in the design phase and the current consumption during in-use stage² [15]. The energy performance gap causes are many and varied and may appear at different stages of the building lifecycle phases (Figure 9). These causes range from an inaccurate energy simulation during the design phase, through poor quality control during the construction phase, incomplete or inadequate commissioning step and finally the operational use of the building (operation, management and occupant). Therefore the GAP is the difference between the prediction of energy consumption and the actual situation. Although in theory the GAP can be positive or negative, in practice it is almost always positive; actual performance turns out much worse than expected; which is rather a fact of human nature.

If one takes a closer look to the roots of this divergence then one can identify a number of reasons relating to the GAP that include:

- **Erroneous simulations** (simulation gap); the simulation software, as efficient as it may be (DOE-2, EnergyPlus, TRNSYS, ESP-r to name but a few), always includes an inherent simulation error. The simulation process involves several different phases required to reach a result: the technological object is replaced (simulated) by a theoretical model, next by a mathematical model, then by a numerical model and lastly by an algorithmic model. Following these different phases of transformations/translations/simulations, some hypotheses and approximations are taken and these choices may generate some bias into the model. Moreover the software is limited in representing the building's innovative design features (such as radiant floors for instance) [16]. Some of the innovative systems (underfloor-air, displacement ventilation, natural ventilation, heat exchange with neighbouring building etc.) are actually poorly represented in the simulation software. Moreover, lighting and plug-loads can be quite different from the input in the design model because most of the time real usage is not known at the time of design, contributing at least partially to deviations between measurements and predictions. For instance, the significantly higher lighting and plug-loads reduce the heating loads and increase the cooling loads. The uncertainty in weather prediction has also a strong impact on simulation results. Weather plays a unique and significant role as it directly affects the thermal loads and thus energy performance of buildings [17]. Some authors say that a good model is accurate within 20% of the actual annual energy consumption, and a calibrated model is accurate within 5-10% of actual annual energy consumption. Although for low energy buildings it becomes more challenging as small differences have a larger percentage impact. A calibrated model involves a process of using genuine as-built information, surveys and measured data to update the input parameters of the initial simulation model so that it closely represents the real operation of the building [18], [19].
- **Construction practices** that differ from those prescribed (build / retrofit gap); construction practices were just not as optimal as considered in design. The theoretical energy use calculated on the basis of building plans and specifications, in order to meet building regulations or requirements by the builder, determines the anticipated performance. It may

² "the difference between the initial calculations carried out in the design of a building compared to the actual energy recorded on utility meters can be several times greater; this is referred to as the 'Performance Gap' [15]

differ from the actual 'as-built' performance in a significant way due to the conductivity of thermal bridges, conductivity of insulation, value of infiltration or U-Values of walls and windows [20]. The issue of construction elements and materials used in building seems to have decisive role in generating the gap between the envisaged and real building energy performance. For instance, the shell does not perform as modelled in the simulation because its implementation is never achieved in a perfect way. The defaults in building during the construction phase and also the poor maintenance and regulation of the HVAC systems play a major role on the simulation accuracy. Nevertheless, it is not easy to predict or control the influence of building components on its energy performance.

- **Numerous operational issues** that create wastage events that deteriorate the performance, well beyond the expectations (operation gap); devices as well as users do not operate as optimally as expected in design. Gaps in this area are usually the more pronounced ones. Occupant action behavior in residential buildings as well as in tertiary buildings affects building performance significantly. Buildings' usage patterns and occupants' behaviour are undoubtedly among the most influential factors affecting buildings energy consumption within its operational phase. Usage patterns of buildings and related occupants behaviour are very difficult to predict, as they are dynamic summaries of individual occupants' interventions and choices, which are not always reasonable and often spontaneous. Occupant behaviour is an investigation subject of many research teams, although, the existing studies on occupant behaviour are carried out mainly from the perspective of sociology and they lack in in-depth quantitative analysis, which is crucial in terms of developing any simulation models. The influence of occupant behavior is under-recognized or over-simplified in the design of buildings. The occupant behavior models developed by different researchers are often inconsistent, with a lack of consensus in common language, in good experimental design and in modelling methodologies. The challenge of complex definition and simulation of occupant behaviour in a consistent and standard way has been targeted by the project Annex 66 [21]. This project aims at delivering simulation methodology with the reference to occupant behaviour in office, residential and commercial buildings.

Thus, reducing the GAP may be achieved by means of interventions along any of these three fundamental life-cycle directions (design, build, operate).

Figure 10: The performance gap between the design and operation of building's energy performance

The performance gap could also be defined as a sum of mistakes during the construction process [22] and misuse of building during the operation phase that widening the gap between energy planned and actual energy consumed. Figure 10 shows how increases the energy consumed in each stage in the case of non-residential buildings and highlights the operation phase impact on the Energy Performance Gap. The HIT2GAP project tries to tackle this GAP focusing on the commissioning and operation phases providing tools able to improve models and simulations and deliver information and ways of managing and optimising energy use to buildings' occupants and BMS.

Figure 11: The Performance Gap Growth from Design to operation [15]

For this purpose, HIT2GAP delivers modules (see section 2) that will provide better assessment of energy use within a building in order to minimize the gap between the theoretical and measured values at different level of actions:

- At the simulation level by integrating the BPS tools within the building operation phase creating a positive loop between operation phase and design phase,
- At the operation level by providing tools allowing:
 - the detection and diagnosis of faults in the systems' functioning,
 - the prediction of energy use and this way an opportunity to anticipate the adjustments of parameters,
 - a better understanding of the energy consumptions (through measurements, advanced analysis of these measurements and usage patterns and occupant behaviour analysis) and therefore the possibility to implement an improved management/piloting of the installations and buildings through the implementation of an ISO 50001 approach for instance.

The modules comprising HIT2GAP have an important impact in controlling and reducing the GAP. **This relationship is described, module by module in the following table.**

Table 2: List of modules proposed in HIT2GAP

	Modules <i>(ambitioned in the proposal)</i>	Module	Ambition	Lifecycle	Description
1	Data enriched simulation tool and BIM	Building Performance Simulation	AMBITION 4: Building performance simulation	DESIGN / OPERATION	<p>The discrepancy between design intents and actual performance (performance gap) is identified by comparing simulation results to measurement data.</p> <p>The reasons for the performance gap (e.g. incorrect modelling assumptions, improper operation) can be specified by analysing in detail the observed discrepancies</p> <p>The performance gap can be mediated by adjusting the simulation model or adjusting the operation accordingly.</p>
2	Disaggregation	Dis-aggregation	AMBITION 3: Data driven models and load forecasting	OPERATION	<p>Dis-aggregation can provide insight on the performance and maintenance needs of electric appliances. And it can do so with lean and cost effective monitoring, sparing the need for costly and intrusive sub metering.</p> <p>Clearly dis-aggregation is not restricted to electric loads; it can well expand on thermal, etc. loads. However the great and increasing number of motors and electric appliances in our building stock makes it particular meaningful in the case of electricity.</p> <p>By its definition dis-aggregation primarily linked to maintenance, to early fault diagnosis and early action on the side of the facility manager.</p> <p>Thus, its potential for gap reduction is closely linked to the <u>maintenance</u> requirements of a given building context; in small residences dis-aggregation may be of low relevance, although it can still</p>

				<p>be meaningful in extracting some <u>useful information for the building user.</u></p> <p>In larger and more complex contexts its importance may significantly rise. Here, large economies may result if faults are easily identified in a timely fashion.</p> <p>As a second impact dimension, dis-aggregation may also make sense for the user behaviour, i.e., it might be that the device information is insightful to the user, highlighting to him instances of wastage, etc. As already implied above, this aspect may be more relevant in the case of residences.</p>
3	Use patterns	Behaviour module	<p>AMBITION 4: Building performance simulation</p> <p>AMBITION 5 Usage patterns / occupants behaviour</p> <p>AMBITION 6: Modular information display</p>	<p>OPERATION Users engage in all sorts of wasteful behaviour practices; they may leave the lights open in empty spaces, they may leave the thermostats high in empty spaces again, etc.</p> <p>In HIT2GAP the behaviour module defines four types of user behaviour related wastage events, senses them, upon their occurrence, and then</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • either notifies the user in the hope that this information will contribute to him reconsidering his bad practice • or may also implement some technology intervention that seeks to address the wastage event and reacts to it <p>Thus, via notification/ technology user behaviour may be much affected towards a more saving profile. As literature reports altering behaviour may result to significant economies that may rise up to 30-40%, although this is difficult to estimate and obviously depends on many parameters.</p> <p>The behaviour module is... modular and can easily accommodate further events, while still making use of the same management and</p>

					<p>notification mechanism that will be developed for this first set of events.</p> <p>In addition to such events HITGAP develops state of the art knowledge also on mood simulation and monitoring.</p> <p>Being able to understand and eventually affect mood holds also potential for savings, although more difficult to calculate and assess as this topic is only recently emerging in the literature.</p>
4	EnMS, Embedded ISO 50001 management	Energy management	AMBITION 3: Data driven models and load forecasting	OPERATION	<p>The Energy Management (EnMS) modules, within the HIT2GAP platform, will provide the tools to develop an overall systematic approach to Energy Management based on ISO 50001, the global energy management systems standard. The ISO 50001 standard specifies requirements for establishing, implementing, maintaining and improving the EMS and the overall building energy performance.</p> <p>The ISO 50001 based EnMS modules within the HIT2GAP platform will help to establish policies and procedures to systematically track, analyze and improve energy efficiency in the buildings.</p> <p>IN HIT2GAP, the EnMS modules provide building owners/managers the tools to review energy use, consumption and overall efficiency; set energy saving targets; identify energy saving opportunities; priorities and develop actions plans to meet targets for improved building energy performance; document the methodology and criteria used and prompt for review at defined intervals; establish energy baselines and Energy Performance Indicators (EnPI) for monitoring, measuring and improving energy performance.</p> <p>The ISO 50001 based EnMS modules when combined with BAS / BMS modules with the HIT2GAP platform provides a comprehensive modern solution to control, monitor, manage and improve building energy performance.</p>

5	Data based load forecast	Forecasting	AMBITION 3: Data driven models and load forecasting	OPERATION	EW-S can forecast availability of thermal and electrical renewable energy at an hourly level. Such information can be communicated with users to avoid energy consumption from the grid thus reducing CO ₂ emissions.
6	Fault detection and diagnosis	Fault detection and diagnosis (FDD)	AMBITION 3: Data driven models and load forecasting	OPERATION	<p>Operational faults are detected by checking measurement data against a model (simulation model, rule-based method, data-driven model).</p> <p>The detected faults can be assigned to a specific part of the system or a set of responsible sensors.</p> <p>The information automatically generated by data analysis methods and possibly additional expert knowledge lead to a fault diagnosis.</p> <p>According to the fault diagnosis warnings and recommendations for the facility management are generated and thus support an energy-efficient fault-free operation. For example, EW-S can provide real-time performance of in-situ installed RET system and its components. Such information is used to detect faults in RET systems and their components.</p>
7	Use patterns	Multiple set-point control	AMBITION 3: Data driven models and load forecasting	OPERATION	<p>The more affordable strategy (algorithms) for indoor thermal comfort (control) of individual building spaces (rooms or zones) are performed - for indoor temperature and humidity - according to different set-point (economy, stand-by, comfort) to take account of variable occupancy profiles of human behaviour within the building space</p> <p>This functionality, although packaged as a separate module is also part of the behaviour module and relates, in particular, to one of its embedded events. Therefore, its relevance to the GAP reduction is not further discussed here as it has already been elaborated above.</p> <p>The module has capability to generate higher energy savings than the</p>

					<p>single or two set-point controllers, while maintaining optimal indoor comfort.</p> <p>The module introduces innovation and progress beyond the commercial state of the art of existing Building Management Systems (BMS).</p>
8		Uncertainty assessment in simulations	AMBITION 4: Building performance simulation	DESIGN / OPERATION	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Accounting for uncertain input parameters (like weather or user behaviour) in simulation models makes design intents more reliable (margin instead of single value). 2. Comparison of simulation results with actual operation (for estimation of performance gap) reveals whether operation lies within margins of design intent. 3. Sensitivity analysis indicates most influential parameters for optimization during design or operation.
9	Technical manager oriented information display	BIM	AMBITION 6: Modular information display	OPERATION	<p>The use of BIM in the HIT2GAP project is as an end user visualization tool.</p> <p>The tool will allow end users to view simulated, historical and live data via a 3D model.</p> <p>The model will be hosted on an app available to download to iOS, android, PC or Mac and will be loaded into the system via an .IFC model type.</p> <p>Having the the ability to navigate through 3D spaces and view and compare energy usage and temperatures in a space will allow the end user to quickly identify problem areas or assets by simple colour coding of those areas. There will also be timeline functionality so you can look at particular dates or average readings between 2 dates.</p> <p>Simple visualization of the data is imperative to allow all users to interact simply with the combined data.</p>

10	Renewable demand / supply management	RET Simulation	AMBITION 4: Building performance simulation	DESIGN / OPERATION	<p>The EW-S simulator provides optimal sizing of RETs systems and its components in new installations and retrofits based on user preferences. The EW-S users are Building Managers, Energy Consultants, RET System Designers and manufacturers.</p> <p>Even though EW-S has been tested in pilots and proved to be accurate, it remains a static simulator which is based on user information for new buildings or historical data for existing building. It cannot predict any future energy usage changes.</p> <p>EW-S can also predict any actions required for RET retrofits, maintenance and performance problem identifications. It can use BMS historical and real-time data from thermal and electrical energy producing and consuming devices to identify:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Real-time performance of in-situ installed RET system and its components 2. Early fault detection in RET systems 3. Changes in thermal and electrical energy usage produced from RETs <p>In addition, actual historical and real-time user behavioural data if available from Hit2Gap platform of the thermal and electrical energy usage are important to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. identify any retrofits required for RET systems based on changes in thermal and electrical energy consumptions 2. identify any replacement required for RET systems with new ones based on critical changes in actual financial user preferences 3. train the EW-S Simulator using actual performance data of the RET systems in specific locations and buildings types 4. avoid CO₂ emissions through behavioral change in using renewable energy instead of electrical power from the grid
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6 Conclusions

This deliverable introduces a general view of the HIT2GAP platform functionality, and briefly introduces the key technology components that pertain to it. Such are the various energy modelling tools integrated, an advanced view of user behaviour, its relevance to energy management, etc. In addition, the HIT2GAP contribution to the reduction of the so called “gap”, i.e., the deviation between the prediction and actual building energy performance, is analysed.

HIT2GAP holds a great potential. On the one hand, it aspires to develop a state of the art OS like environment that will be able to seamlessly accommodate diverse third party applications. On the other hand it looks forward to develop technology in areas that are key in the building energy domain, such as simulation, energy modelling, behaviour, disaggregation.

In short, HIT2GAP will emerge as an open platform offering high added value to third parties as well as tangible, state of the art functionality that will both allow to reduce the GAP between the predicted and actual performance.

In this sense, WP1 is a key milestone towards fully designing this advanced HIT2GAP environment.

7 Acronyms and abbreviations

AEC	Architecture, Engineering and Construction
API	APINTECH
BAS	Building Automation System
BES	Bouygues Energie et Services
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BMS	Building Management System
BPS	Building Performance Simulation
BRE	Building Research Establishment
DOA	Description of the action
EC	European Commission
EGE	Ege University
ENE	ENERIT
EnMS	Energy Management System
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EU	European Union
EUR	EURECAT
EW-S	Energy Warden Simulator
FDD	Fault Detection & Diagnosis
FISE	Fraunhofer ISE
IPMVP	International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol
LIU	LIUPPA Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour
MOS	MOSTOSTAL
NBK	NOBATEK
RET	Renewable Energy Tool
SBEM	Simplified Building Energy Model
UDG	University Of Girona
UOS	University Of Strathclyde

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